

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

Document ID: D4.3 Final release of AI-based solutions for time series and imaging data analysis

30/01/2024

RAMONES funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive programme via grant agreement No.101017808

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	RAMONES		
Name	Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems		
Start Date	1 Jan 2021	End Date	31 Dec 2024
Program	H2020-EU.1.2.2. - FET Proactive		
Call ID	H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2	Topic	FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020 - Environmental Intelligence
Grant No	101017808	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D4.3		
Document Title	Final release of AI-based solutions for time series and imaging data analysis		
Due Date	31-Dec-2023	Delivery Date	30-01-2024
Lead Beneficiary	NTUA (5)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA (1), IST-ID (2), PLOA (6)		
Editor(s)	Valsamis Ntouskos, Konstantinos Karantzalos (NTUA)		
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Reviewer(s)	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)		
Workpackages	WP4 - Multi-modal Data Analytics and Environmental Modelling		
Version	v1.0	Stage	Submission
Distribution	Public		
Keywords	Pathfinder, EIC, FET, Radioactivity, Environmental Intelligence, Underwater Research, Architecture, γ -radiation, Spectrometers	Type	Other

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor
0.1	1/3/2023	First draft report's structure	NTUA
0.2	20/4/2023	Updates after the Milos Field trip	NTUA
0.3	5/5/2023	Revisions and updates in all subsections	NTUA
1.0	12/7/2023	Document version submitted to EC	NKUA
1.1	12/12/2023	Preparation of new release	NTUA
1.2	14/12/2023	Adding updated information about SUGI and CHERI	NTUA
1.3	18/12/2023	Adding hardware implementation section	NTUA
1.4	23/12/2023	Final adjustments	NTUA
1.5	15/1/2024	Minor corrections, Internal review	NTUA
1.6	28/1/2024	Adding appendix and novel pooling methods	NTUA
	30/1/2024	Deliverable submitted	

Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable, and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
ASV	Autonomous Surface Vehicle
AttMask	Attention-guided Masking
CPS	Counts per second
HW	Hardware
LLD	Low-Level Discriminator
MIM	Masked Image Modeling
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NORM	Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
(R)MSE	(Root) Mean Squared Error
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SoA	State of the art
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
ViT	Vision Transformers

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the AI-based software solutions developed for processing the data produced by the RAMONES instruments. Specifically, software for preprocessing and analysing radioactivity measurements (time-series) collected from the γ Sniffers has been developed. Additionally, a custom API and dedicated software modules have been developed for collecting and processing individual radioactivity detection events registered by SUGI, for radioactivity imaging using Compton imaging. The document also presents a high-level simulation environment that has been built to study the ability to detect and map radioactivity in large volumes of water from the measurements collected by γ Sniffers mounted on the underwater gliders, under different considerations regarding the trajectories of the gliders, their spacing and the form of the radioactivity distribution. Testing and validation aspects using data collected during field deployments are also discussed, together with integration aspects on the computational platforms of the RAMONES vehicles.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

This report is the deliverable D4.3 “*Final release of AI-based solutions for time series and imaging data analysis*” of the H2020 RAMONES project. The report is a product of the work performed in WP4 “*Multi-modal Data Analytics and Environmental Modelling*” in a tight conjunction with the concurrent activities performed also in WP1 “*Design and Develop Novel Underwater Gamma Radiation Instruments*”, WP2 “*Autonomous Marine Robotics for Collaborative Radioactivity Mapping*” and WP3 “*Onsite Integration, Testing and Pilot Demonstrators*”. An updated version of this document is planned to be submitted within M42 to cover the validation of the finalized versions of the AI software components, on the RAMONES vehicles tested on a relevant environment.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

The main purpose of the present document is to present the software solutions that have been developed for analysing the data collected from the instruments developed in the project. The developed solutions consider the characteristics of each instrument and the corresponding data modalities. Specifically, γ Sniffers produce time-series reporting number (counts) of detected gamma ray events in a specific time interval, potentially with associated photon energies. SUGI, besides number of events, provides imaging information, thanks to its pixelated detector modules.

A novel high-level simulation environment is described first, which allows to simulate the data collected by the γ Sniffers mounted on the underwater gliders, considering basic models for radioactivity interactions with matter under reference distributions, for typical forms of glider trajectories used to scan the volume of interest. Subsequently, AI-based methods developed for time-series data analysis are first described, followed by methods for processing the data collected by the imaging sensors. The document also discusses the integration of these solutions in the hardware processing platforms implemented in RAMONES.

1.3. Structure of the document

Chapter 2 presents the high-level simulation developed for studying detection and mapping of radioactivity using underwater gliders. Chapter 3 describes the AI-based solutions developed for the processing of time-dependent radioactivity measurements, while Chapter 4 discusses the algorithms developed to support radioactivity imaging. Chapter 5 presents the testing and validation of the developed methods based on data collected during field deployments, while Chapter 6 discusses hardware integration aspects. Chapter 7 provides concluding remarks.

2. High-level Simulation for Multi-modal Data Analytics and Environmental Modelling

In this chapter, a high-level simulation environment is presented that has been developed for providing simulated radioactivity measurements for different types of radioactive sources considering typical trajectories followed by underwater gliders, based on their kinematic model. In particular, simplified models are considered both for the radioactivity measurement and the movement of the gliders (e.g., absence of localization uncertainty). The goal is to provide an environment where different radioactivity detection and mapping scenarios can be tried out, allowing to choose suitable scanning patterns and better understanding limitations due to challenges from radioactivity shielding of the water and the significantly small coverage of the area of interest. The simulator has been developed in Python, both for the graphical representations, and for the numerical simulations of the measured radioactivity values.

2.1. Environment and Glider Trajectories

A reference volume of interest has been defined in the form of a three-dimensional cuboid with a size of 3000x3000x300 meters (x, y, z axes, respectively), as shown in Figure 1. The simulation is performed in a 1:1 scale.

Figure 1: Volume of interest

In this reference volume, two types of underwater glider trajectories are considered. The first corresponds to diagonal (zigzag) vertical motion and the other to spiral movements, as shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4. The simulation considers different spacing between the trajectories. For the diagonal movement, the horizontal distance between two trajectories is

defined as trajectory spacing. For the spiral movement, the original volume is divided into smaller sub-volumes, based on a horizontal spacing. The radius of the spiral movement is defined as $\frac{1}{4}$ of the size of this horizontal spacing. The vertical movement of the underwater gliders is limited to the range [25, 285], considering suitable margins for safe operation.

Figure 2: Presentation of diagonal trajectories in the simulation environment

Figure 3: Presentation of spiral trajectories in the simulation environment

Figure 4: Top-view of diagonal and spiral trajectories in the simulation environment

The type of glider movement has an important impact on the time required to execute the trajectory and to the percentage of coverage of the volume of interest. The simulation environment allows to estimate the time needed to scan the entire volume. Given a specific type of movement, providing the value of the trajectory spacing, the volume is filled with the planned trajectories, allowing to compute total length of the resulting scan-path. Dividing the scan-path length by the speed of underwater gliders (e.g., $v=0.5$ m/s) the duration of the scan can be estimated. Additionally, considering a maximum detection range for the radioactivity detectors mounted on the gliders (e.g., $r=1$ m based on preliminary results for point sources), the volume of the space measured can be reported in relation to the total scan volume. Table 1 and Table 2 report indicative values for $v=0.5$ m/s and $r=1$ m.

Table 1: Characteristics of diagonal trajectories

Trajectory Spacing (m)	Total Distance (km)	Estimated Time	Coverage Rate (%)
100 x 100	221.2	5d & 2:53h	0.025
150 x 150	151.8	3d & 12:19h	0.017
200 x 200	117.1	2d & 17:02h	0.013
250 x 250	96.3	2d & 5:28h	0.011

Table 2: Characteristics of spiral trajectories

Voxel Spacing (m)	Total Distance (km)	Estimated Time	Coverage Rate (%)
200 x 200	362.2	8d & 9:13h	0.042
300 x 300	229.6	5d & 7:32h	0.026
400 x 400	146.7	3d & 9:30h	0.017
500 x 500	133.2	3d & 2:00h	0.015

2.2. Types of Radioactivity sources and Measurement Models

Different types of radioactivity sources are considered, ranging from point sources to radioactivity distributions covering partly or entirely the volume of interest.

Point sources

This simplified model can be used as a good approximation when the size of the source is much smaller compared to the distance at which measurements are recorded. Due to the reduction of the solid angle in which the detector observes the source, the intensity of radioactivity emitted by a point source and reaching the detector is subject to the inverse square law. Therefore, as we move away from the point source, the intensity of the radioactivity decreases according to the square of the distance. Another factor that significantly affects radioactivity detection is shielding from the material between the source and the detector. Due to shielding, the intensity of radioactivity decreases exponentially according to an attenuation factor that depends on the density and the physical properties of the material in which it transports. There are other factors that affect radioactivity detection, such as build-up factor, which were not considered as they contribute less to the simulated measurements.

Based on these factors, the intensity of the measured radioactivity I_R at a certain point at a distance R (for R a few times larger than the detector size) from a point source of intensity I_0 can be approximated by the following formula:

$$I_R = \frac{I_0}{R^2} \cdot e^{-\mu \cdot R} \quad (1)$$

Table 3: Comparison of radioactivity attenuation in air and in water

Distance [m]	Attenuation factor	
	Air ($\rho=1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$) ($\mu/\rho=0.0636 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, $\mu \simeq 0.0078 \text{ m}^{-1}$)	Water ($\rho=1.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$) ($\mu/\rho=0.0707 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, $\mu \simeq 7.2 \text{ m}^{-1}$)
0.25	0.998	0.165
0.5	0.996	0.027
1	0.992	7.4e-4
2	0.985	5.4e-7
5	0.962	2.2e-16
10	0.925	4.8e-32

Table 3 provides a comparison of the attenuation factor in the air and inside the water, considering shielding alone. One can see that detection of point sources in the water is extremely challenging due to the very effective shielding of radioactivity from water.

Distribution Sources

Another scenario of interest is the mapping of radioactivity in the water column in large areas. To examine this possibility, we consider different distributions of radioactivity in the water, and use the simulator to examine how accurately these distributions can be reconstructed from radioactivity measurements acquired from an underwater glider traversing through them, considering different scan strategies.

The following reference distributions were examined, which offer different characteristics in terms of geometry and spatial frequencies. For simplicity, the detector is assumed to directly measure the quantity of interest, without any loss or noise affecting the measurement. In case the distribution does not cover the entire space, a static background 10 times smaller than the signal is assumed.

Analytical distributions

Analytical distributions have been considered, as they are defined by mathematical formulas, hence their properties can be accurately recovered.

One reference distribution examined is the following:

$$I(x, y, z) = \sin \sqrt{\left(\frac{x - 1500}{150}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y - 1500}{150}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z - 150}{15}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: Graphical representation of relation (3)

In Figure 5, the graphical representation of the reference distribution of relation (3) is presented. We notice that the specific function completely covers the area of interest, having several changes in terms of the returned values depending on the position.

One more reference distribution examined is the one presented in Figure 6 and relation (4). This function also covers the entire volume of interest. It follows a pattern as the values increase as the z-axis value increases.

$$I(x, y, z) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{x}{3000}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{3000}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{300}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 6: Graphical representation of relation (4)

Diffusion-based sources

Another important scenario considers the diffusion of radioactive material around a source, as for example in the case of a hydrothermal plume. Fick's law describes the flow of particles or some substance in a propagation medium. According to Fick's law, the rate of diffusion depends entirely on the degree of concentration of the substance. Letting J be the diffusion rate, D the diffusion coefficient, C the concentration of the substance and x the distance along the diffusion axis, Fick's law is expressed mathematically by the following expression:

$$J = -D \cdot \frac{dC}{dx} \quad (5)$$

In real world, the concentration of a substance is not constant, since it changes with respect to time and space, due to the continuous production or consumption of the substance. To express this phenomenon, Fick's law is modified as follows:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = D \cdot \frac{d^2C}{dx^2} \quad (6)$$

Relation (6) constitutes Fick's second law. The analytical form of Fick's second law, presented in relation (7), is considered to simulate diffusion of radioactivity in the water. $C(x, t)$ is the concentration of the substance at point x and time t , C_0 is the initial concentration of the substance, C_s is the concentration of the substance at point x , while $\text{erf}(x)$ is the error function.

$$C(x, t) = C_s - (C_s - C_0) \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{Dt}}\right) \quad (7),$$

where
$$\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x \exp(-u^2) du \quad (8)$$

In the simulations, the radioactivity diffusion that corresponds to 4000 timesteps around a cylinder with constant concentration equal to 100 is considered. These results to a radioactivity distribution with values in the range $[0, 100]$, as can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Diffusion effect

Plume

A geometric representation of a hydrothermal plume is also considered. This is modelled as a truncated conical shape. A three-dimensional inverted cone is considered placed at the center of the bottom of the simulation environment ($x = 1500, y = 1500$). Inside the cone, the returned values are equal to 10, while outside it is equal to 1. Finally, the radius of the cone at its base is $R_b = 80$, while the radius at the highest point is $R_t = 300$ (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Graphical representation of plume in the environment of simulation

3. AI-based solutions for time series analysis

We report on the developed software for the analysis of time series data acquired mainly from the γ Sniffers instruments. The considered datasets are derived from the developed simulated environment as well as the real data that were acquired during the Milos field campaigns.

3.1. Processing of measurements

Measurements from γ Sniffers are stored in *.spe files in regular intervals, containing details about the energy of the events recorded in the corresponding temporal interval, as well as meta-data regarding the operating parameters and conditions of the detector. The detected events are correlated with the position of the glider at the same time interval together with the corresponding uncertainties, based on the localization algorithms developed in the project. Radioactivity mapping considers these combined time-series (detected events and localization) in order to produce a map of the radioactivity distribution in the underwater volume being scanned. Even without considering uncertainties in the estimated location of the gliders, the problem is notoriously challenging, as measurements cover an infinitesimal portion of the scanned volume, as shown in Section 3.1. This is inherent to the problem having co-dimension 2, as measurements are virtually 1-dimensional, due also to the locality of measurements caused by water shielding, and the scanned volume being 3-dimensional. The most obvious solution to propagate measurements to the volume of interest in order to provide a radioactivity map is through interpolation of the recorded values. The simulation environment described in Section 3, was used to assess the accuracy of the maps reconstructed through interpolation, as well as their efficiency. Although the interpolation results were satisfactory, their computation is very demanding due to the very high number of measurements involved and the large extent of the volume needed to be filled through interpolation. To address these challenges, a novel MLP-based sparse measurement interpolation method was developed, described in the following section.

3.2. MLP-based sparse measurements interpolation

Model

The idea of using an MLP for interpolating values from a highly complex function builds on the work of NeRF [1], where a method for synthesizing complex scenes was developed using a continuous function defined based on a sparse set of input values. In fact, a function of interest can be approximated in arbitrary precision by an MLP, according to the universal approximation theorem. In this context one can optimize the weights of an MLP by providing

the function argument as input and using the measured (or computed) value of the function as supervision. In practice, it has been found that MLPs are not capable of learning high degree functions from low-dimensional inputs. This difficulty can be overcome by applying positional encoding to the input, which artificially increases the dimensionality of the input through the use of Fourier features [2]. In the context of radioactivity mapping, using an MLP as a function approximator and, subsequently as an interpolator through querying values at specific locations, leads to an improvement in the accuracy as well as a significant reduction of the required execution time.

As a reference architecture, an MLP with four hidden layers was considered, of which the first three consist of 256 neurons, while the third one consists of 128 neurons. The ReLU activation function was considered for the hidden layers. The MLP is optimized considering the mean-squared error with respect to the measured values in the corresponding spatial locations. A small portion of the available data is considered as validation data and an early stopping strategy is implemented, with patience equal to 7 seasons. The early stopping helps to prevent the model from overfitting, thus allowing better approximation of values far from the measured locations. Based on the discussion, the three-dimensional input coordinates are transformed using Positional encoding based on Fourier Features.

Results

To assess radioactivity mapping algorithms, the simulation environment presented in Section 3 was used, considering different types of underwater glider trajectories and different radioactivity distributions. A grid of query coordinates was considered consisting of $31 \times 31 \times 8 = 7688$ regularly spaced points. It should be noted that the aim was to keep a reasonable trade-off between horizontal (XY plane) and vertical (Z axis) resolution due to memory restrictions. Based on the considered volume size and use cases it was much more costly to improve the horizontal resolution than the vertical. Therefore, the spatial resolution in XY was $\sim 100\text{m}$ and in Z it was as dense as possible based on computational constraints.

In particular, the points are equally spaced in 31 intervals along the x and y axes in the range $[0, 3000]$ and in 8 equally spaced intervals along the z axis in the range $[0, 300]$. The grid size was chosen with the rationale of having enough points to produce a reconstruction accurate and detailed enough, but also with a number of points as small as possible, as typical implementations (e.g., function 'griddata' of SciPy in Python) are very demanding computationally and an excessive number of query points is prohibitive due to space and time constraints. Table 4 and Table 5 present the root-mean square error (RMSE) and peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) metrics, typical metrics used for assessing signal reconstruction quality,

for the estimated radioactivity maps computed using linear interpolation for diagonal (zigzag) and spiral glider trajectories, respectively. The name of the experimental setup reports the corresponding trajectory spacing and the type of radioactivity distribution considered.

Table 4: Radioactivity mapping using diagonal (zigzag) trajectories

Setup	RMSE	MSE	PSNR	Time (sec)
100x100_cone	0.435	0.19	26.309	4517.82
150x150_cone	0.448	0.201	26.058	3685.19
200x200_cone	0.455	0.207	25.922	6208.8
250x250_cone	0.485	0.235	25.373	2474.45
300x300_cone	0.465	0.217	25.729	2489.56
100x100_diffused	1.254	1.573	37.946	4714.56
150x150_diffused	1.282	1.643	37.757	3189.47
200x200_diffused	1.995	3.979	33.915	6514.14
250x250_diffused	1.467	2.153	36.582	2365.43
300x300_diffused	1.756	3.085	35.02	2126.22
100x100_distrib	0.392	0.153	14.164	4781.69
150x150_distrib	0.455	0.207	12.867	3081.06
200x200_distrib	0.526	0.276	11.609	6601.45
250x250_distrib	0.526	0.276	11.607	2692.13
300x300_distrib	0.562	0.315	11.031	2432.46

Table 5: Radioactivity mapping using spiral trajectories

Setup	RMSE	MSE	PSNR	Time (sec)
200x200_cone	0.364	0.132	27.863	8903.57
300x300_cone	0.451	0.203	26.003	2063.71
400x400_cone	0.556	0.309	24.191	1566.98
500x500_cone	0.584	0.341	23.757	901.47

600x600_cone	0.617	0.381	23.275	1350.45
200x200_diffused	0.966	0.933	40.213	9747.65
300x300_diffused	1.928	3.718	34.209	1775.19
400x400_diffused	1.83	3.351	34.661	1691.73
500x500_diffused	2.9	8.413	30.663	863.36
600x600_diffused	2.732	7.465	31.182	1166.25
200x200_distrib	0.2	0.04	19.996	9425.7
300x300_distrib	0.273	0.074	17.31	2059.14
400x400_distrib	0.353	0.124	15.073	1696.59
500x500_distrib	0.366	0.134	14.746	893.72
600x600_distrib	0.392	0.153	14.162	1308.94

We note that the radioactivity distribution based on diffusion is better approximated. This can be attributed to the fact that changes in the radioactivity values are quite small. Plume (conical) distribution gives the second-best results, while the analytical distribution of relation (4) is the most challenging, most probably due to the large extent of spatial frequencies (periodicity of the signal in space; essentially its Fourier components) that the signal contains. In terms of the glider trajectories used for scanning the volume, the best results are obtained with the spiral motion and voxel spacing equal to 200 x 200, at the cost of excessively long time to complete the mapping. Diagonal movement, on the other hand, provides slightly worse results but with the important advantage of reduced scan time.

The last column of Table 4 and Table 5 reports the time required to execute the linear interpolation on the 31x31x8 grid on a typical workstation. This time ranges from 15 minutes to approximately 3 hours. The time required to complete the interpolation task is directly related to the trajectory and the number of query locations. These extended computation times are also one of the reasons we have developed the MLP-based interpolation method.

Figure 9 and Figure 10, show the performance comparison of the MLP-based interpolation with respect to the linear interpolation baseline using the PSNR metric, for the diagonal and spiral movements, respectively. One can see that MLP gives comparable performance with the linear based interpolation in the case of diagonal trajectories, while they lead to significantly better performance when spiral trajectories are used. As expected, the smallest voxel spacing, i.e., 200m x 200m, leads to the best results, from the cases considered.

Importantly, the execution time of MLP-based interpolation is sped-up multiple times with respect to linear-based interpolation. In particular, the time required for MLP-based interpolation for the scenarios we considered range from 18 to 369 seconds with an average of 101 seconds. Compared to the corresponding linear interpolation times, this corresponds to a speedup in the worst case of 8 and in the best case of 26 times.

Figure 9: Comparison of linear and MLP-based interpolation results for diagonal movement

Figure 10: Comparison of linear and MLP-based interpolation results for spiral movement

4. AI-based solutions for imaging

At this release we report on the developed software for the analysis of imaging data acquired mainly from the SUGI instrument. The datasets used are derived from experimental setups in the laboratory and from the Milos field campaign. Moreover, state of the art AI methods have been designed and developed able to exploit mix-up and powerful attention mechanisms in imaging data with deep vision transformers.

4.1. Metric learning and cutting-edge attention mechanisms

Initially, based on the estimation that the number/size of RAMONES imaging datasets will not be huge in size and adequate to train from scratch deep neural network architectures with numerous parameters, we considered and studied state of the art data augmentation techniques, In particular, based on the argument that metric learning is binary classification of pairs of examples into “positive” and “negative”, we have introduced a direct extension of mixup from classification to metric learning. The developed methodology [3] is generic, applying to a large class of loss functions that separate positives from negatives per anchor and involve component functions that are additive over examples. Those are exactly loss functions that require less mining. We have introduced a novel way of interpolating labels, such that the interpolation factor affects the relative weighting of positives and negatives. Other than that, our approach is completely agnostic with respect to the mixup method, opening the way to using more advanced mixup methods for metric learning. Based on an extensive qualitative and quantitative evaluation we have demonstrated that we consistently outperform baselines using a number of loss functions on a number of benchmarks and we improve the state of the art using a single loss function on all benchmarks, while previous state of the art was not consistent in this respect. Moreover, due to the fact that metric learning is about generalizing to unseen classes and distributions, our work may have applications to other such problems, including transfer learning, few-shot learning and continual learning.

Furthermore, we have studied state of the art deep learning frameworks based on vision transformers (ViT). Considering that transformers are data-hungry, many studies advocate pre-training them on unsupervised pretext tasks, determined only by raw data. A prominent paradigm is to mask a portion of the input tokens—words in text or patches in images—and train the transformer to predict these missing tokens. Towards this direction masked image modeling (MIM) based on self-supervised methods have shown impressive results, however, an important aspect that has not been well explored so far is how to choose which image tokens to mask. Thus, we have designed and developed a method [4] that is able to exploit the

intrinsic properties of ViT and in particular, its self-attention mechanism. Given an input sequence of image patches, we forward it through the transformer encoder, thereby obtaining an attention map in its output. We then mask the most attended tokens. This strategy, which we call attention-guided masking (AttMask), is an excellent fit to popular distillation-based self-supervised objectives, because it is the teacher encoder that sees the entire image and extracts the attention map, and the student encoder that sees the masked image and solves the reconstruction task. AttMask thus incurs zero additional cost. In a nutshell: we have introduced a novel masking strategy for self-supervised learning (AttMask), that exploits the intrinsic properties of ViT by leveraging its self-attention maps to guide token masking. We have demonstrated how to efficiently incorporate this above masking strategy into teacher-student frameworks that use a MIM reconstruction objective and demonstrate significant performance improvements over random masking. Moreover, we performed extensive experimental evaluation, and validated that AttMask offers several benefits: it accelerates the learning process; it improves performance on a data-limited regime and on a variety of downstream tasks; it increases the robustness against background changes, thus revealing that it reduces background dependency.

4.2. From cutting-edge attention to novel pooling mechanisms

Moreover, in the framework of WP4, AI-based techniques were further developed based on the outcomes of 4.1. In particular, cutting-edge deep learning techniques were designed and developed addressing RAMONES downstream tasks including novel procedures to compute attention maps in supervised transformers of at least as good quality as self-supervised procedures, without explicit losses or modifying the architecture of the considered models.

To this end, we have introduced *SimPool* [7], a simple, attention-based pooling mechanism that acts at the very last step of either convolutional or transformer encoders, delivering highly superior quantitative results on several benchmarks and downstream tasks. In addition, *SimPool* delivers decent attention maps in both convolutional and transformer networks under both supervision and self-supervision with remarkable improvement in delineating object boundaries for supervised transformers. In order to leverage this novel design for AI-based imaging tasks we have proven that vision transformers can be reformulated in two streams, where one is extracting a visual representation on patch tokens and the other is performing spatial pooling on the CLS token; whereas, convolutional networks undergo global spatial pooling at the very last step, before the classifier. In this sense, one can isolate the pooling process from both kinds of networks and replace it by a new one. Moreover, the main objective of the overall design was to derive a simple pooling process at the very last step of either

convolutional or transformer encoders that improves over their default; to additionally provide high-quality attention maps that delineate object boundaries; to also retain the desired properties under both supervised and self-supervised settings.

Thus, the developed generic pooling framework, was parametrized by: (a) the number of vectors in the pooled representation; (b) whether pooling is iterative or not; (c) mappings at every stage of the process; (d) pairwise similarities, attention function and normalization; and (e) a function determining the pooling operation. The novelty of the developed work summarizes as [7]: 1. We formulate a generic pooling framework that allows easy inspection and qualitative comparison of a wide range of methods. 2. We introduce a simple, attention-based, non-iterative, universal pooling mechanism that provides a single vector representation and answers all the above questions in the affirmative. 3. We conduct an extensive empirical study that validates the superior qualitative properties and quantitative performance of the proposed mechanism on standard benchmarks and downstream tasks.

4.3. Development of the Submarine Gamma Imager

The underwater gamma imager instrument (SUGI) is based on the GDS-100 platform developed by IDEAS AS. GDS-100, being an integrated solution comprising detector modules, acquisition electronics and management PCB in an OEM product, offers an optimal trade-off between customization ability and product maturity. GDS-100 supports up to four GDS-10 detector modules. Each detector module is paired with a 11×11 pixelated CdZnTe (CZT) crystal and has 121+2 detection channels, 121 anode channels for the 11×11 array and 2 special (cathode) channels. This configuration allows to perform Compton imaging by analyzing the spatial and temporal correlation amid the events registered by the device, either within the same detector or across different ones [5]. The use of multiple pixelated detector modules is advantageous as it speeds up the collection of sufficient statistics for reliable localization and identification of nearby radioactivity sources. This is particularly crucial in the underwater setting as the majority of gamma rays arrive at the detector after multiple scattering events.

The SUGI instrument, besides the GDS-100 system, comprises a High Voltage module, necessary for providing suitable bias voltage to the CZT detectors, a Raspberry Pi 4 single-board computer hosting all software necessary for logging, processing, and analyzing all data collected from GDS-100, and auxiliary electronic and network components (i.e., power modules, relays, network switches, etc). All these components are contained in a custom-made underwater housing rated for 1000m depth. The housing thickness and material, as well as the placement of the components in the housing, have been chosen based on simulations

performed in the context of Task 1.2. A solution was chosen that balances between as-small-as-possible gamma radiation absorption while ensuring the aforementioned depth rating. Specifically, an aluminum alloy 6061-T6 of 4 mm thickness has been chosen with a hard anodized treatment for withstanding the expected pressure (100 bar) and the corrosiveness of sea water, especially in highly acid environments as the ones encountered in hydrothermal vents. Figure 11 shows the setup of the internal components of SUGI on the additive manufacturing base designed to fit the dimensions of the underwater housing.

Figure 11: SUGI component setup inside the underwater housing.

The design of SUGI allows the mounting of the instrument both on a static benthic laboratory or on a remotely operated vehicle (ROV). Regarding the first solution, by mounting SUGI on a static underwater platform lying on the seabed, SUGI can perform prolonged measurements collecting data regarding the surrounding radioactivity. Mounting SUGI on an ROV, on the other hand, gives the possibility of moving the instrument in the vicinity of regions of interest where significant radioactivity events are located or suspected. The multipurpose design of SUGI enhances its versatility making it suitable across diverse radioactivity monitoring and mapping scenarios.

Data logging, processing, and communication with the GDS-100 is achieved using the TCP/IP protocol. TCP packets are used for system configuration and UDP packets for data readout. A custom python API has been developed, according to the GDS-100 TCP/UDP packet specifications (Doppio format), to allow real-time configuration, system health monitoring

(e.g., key component voltage, temperatures, etc.), and data readout. A python implementation was favored, to allow easy deployment both on x86-64 desktop/workstation systems for development purposes, and on AARCH64 embedded computers, like Raspberry Pi 4, for testing and final deployment.

Preprocessing software modules have been developed to achieve basic tasks as reporting of total event counts and counts per second, the assignment of recorded events to ADC channels and the construction of the corresponding histogram, as well as the specific anode channels (i.e., pixels) where the event(s) were registered. Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the raw data registered for a single detection event and cumulative pixel activations from background radioactivity registered in the lab using all four ASIC modules of SUGI corresponding to 1000 registered events. From the digitized signals shown on Figure 12, one can observe the charge measured at location (4,5) of the pixelated array as well the corresponding values for the cathode and the neighboring pixels. The latter is due to charge "leaking" from the central pixel caused by the fact that part of the generated electron cloud affects the neighboring pixels too. That phenomenon is dependent on the high-voltage steering grid of the sensor and is exploited in Compton imaging to provide sub-pixel accuracy for the location of the Compton interaction/event. Regarding the cumulative pixel activations shown on Figure 13, one can observe more events being detected by the 4th module (ASIC 3), due to different configuration settings applied to this module.

Figure 12: Data from an event registered by GDS-100

Figure 13: Anode activations of the four ASIC modules of GDS-100

4.4. Development of the Cherenkov Imager

As described in D1.4, two alternative solutions are considered as sensing modules for the CHERI instrument. One relies on a high-resolution, high-sensitivity UV camera, while the other utilizes the Hermes single photon camera produced by Micro Photon Devices. The development of AI-based solutions for the processing of single photon camera has been delayed due to delays in sensor procurement. The device has been procured on M35 and software modules regarding its setup and data logging are currently being developed based on the API provided by the device manufacturer. Suitable AI-based processing of the captured data for enabling the lowest possible detection thresholds for detecting Cherenkov radiation are under development, considering the special characteristics of this device.

Regarding the detection of Cherenkov radiation using the UV camera, state-of-the-art image enhancement methods are used in combination with optics that have high efficiency in the near UV spectrum for significantly enhancing the sensitivity of the camera in the near UV spectrum for increasing the probability of Cherenkov radiation detection.

5. Hardware integration and validation

The current chapter is dedicated to the discussion on the hardware (HW) implementation of the AI-based software stack for the benthic lab instruments, the gliders and the surface vehicle. The implementation, albeit similar for all cases, shows some differences due to variations in the selected computing platform and the role of each asset in the overall deployment setup. Each implementation is described in more detail in the following.

5.1. Hardware platforms

The target HW on which the RAMONES software stack will be executed, including the AI-based algorithms discussed in the previous sections, is based on the ARM64-based architecture. The only exception is the processing module of the UV-camera based implementation of the CHERI instrument which is based on an Intel x86-64 architecture due to driver and SDK restrictions.

Regarding the other instruments of the benthic lab, namely the γ Sniffers and the SUGI, a dedicated data processing module has been developed by PLOA based on a Raspberry Pi 4 single board computer (Figure 14, left). Table 6 summarizes the main specification of this device. This embedded processing device has been selected as it is powerful enough to manage the computational load of the software modules concerning the operation of the instrument and the processing of the data produced by them, with reduced power consumption.

For the vehicles, the RAMONES software stack includes modules mostly based on ROS for the communication setup, logging, sensor data processing and data analysis, as described in detail in deliverable D2.2. Even though the target baseline architecture (ARM64v8) is the same for all vehicles, the embedded devices selected for the glider and the Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV) differ. Specifically, the Raspberry Pi 4 (RPi4) single board computer was selected for the gliders for similar reasons as the ones described above, and because many of the preexisting software modules regarding underwater communication and navigation have been developed and extensively tested on this specific device.

Table 6: Raspberry Pi 4 specifications

Processor	Broadcom BCM2711, quad-core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz
Memory	4GB LPDDR4 with on-die ECC
Connectivity	2.4 GHz and 5.0 GHz IEEE 802.11b/g/n/ac wireless LAN, Bluetooth 5.0, BLE Gigabit Ethernet 2 × USB 3.0 ports, 2 × USB 2.0 ports Standard 40-pin GPIO header

Video	2 × micro HDMI ports (up to 4Kp60 supported) 2-lane MIPI DSI display port 2-lane MIPI CSI camera port
Multimedia	H.265 (4Kp60 decode) H.264 (1080p60 decode, 1080p30 encode) OpenGL ES, 3.0 graphics
Input Power	5V DC via USB-C connector or GPIO header
Implemented OS	Ubuntu 20.04.5 64bit LTS

Regarding the software modules related to the ASV operation, the NVIDIA Jetson Nano¹ device has been chosen (Figure 14, right), which is an embedded processing system with the same architecture to the Raspberry Pi 4 single-board computer (Table 7). The main difference in the Jetson Nano system lies in the fact that it offers a 128Core Maxwell GPU which is suitable for running different AI and ML-based applications, with the price of a slightly higher energy consumption. In combination with the Nvidia Software tools and support for the most well-known AI frameworks available today, the Nvidia Jetson system is an ideal choice for the deployment of ML-based applications for on-board processing of incoming sensor data and autonomous decision-making tasks.

Table 7: Nvidia Jetson Nano Specifications

Processor	Quad-Core ARM Cortex-A57 64-bit @ 1.43 GHz
Memory	4GB LPDDR4
Connectivity	40 x GPIO pins 2 x MIPI CSI-2 DPHY Gigabit Ethernet 4 x USB 3.0 1 x USB 2.0
Video	2 x HDMI 2.0 1 x DisplayPort
Input Power	5V DC via mini-USB or DC-Barrel Jack
Implemented OS	Ubuntu 20.04.5 64bit LTS

¹<https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-nano-developer-kit>

Figure 14: Raspberry Pi 4 (left) and NVIDIA Jetson Nano (right) single-board computers

5.2. Validation of AI-based software in real environments

The developed AI-based software modules integrated in the current version of the benthic lab, were validated in real environments in three distinct cases, which cover the spectrum of targeted operating conditions. The first case was in the field experiments performed in a coastal water setting at Milos island, Greece on March 2023, while the other two were in the context of the scientific expeditions that took place in June and October 2023 in the deep-water setting of the Kolumbo volcano, which is the targeted final deployment environment for RAMONES. In all cases, the processing HW and the implemented AI-based solutions operated without issues, providing important scientific data and crucial information regarding radioactivity in these environments. Detailed information regarding the field deployments at Milos and the expeditions at Kolumbo, together with the analysis of the data collected from all RAMONES instruments deployed in each setting are provided in D3.2.

5.3. Integration and testing of vehicle software stack

The setup of the processing modules for the underwater gliders and the Autonomous Surface Vehicle are described in the following.

Glider Processing Setup

The main processing requirements assigned to the Raspberry Pi 4 systems installed in the glider vehicles are the following:

1. execution of the RAMONES communication stack, based on the IST-ID ROS stack described in D2.2;
2. data collection from the γ Sniffer and local processing and logging of its measurements;

3. extreme event detection from the radioactivity measurements time-series;
4. transferring of radioactivity measurements and localization information to the ASV.

Surface Vehicle Processing Setup

The main tasks for the ASV data processing system include:

1. execution of the RAMONES communication stack;
2. implementation of software modules for navigation/control and 4G communication;
3. gSniffer communication and aggregated data processing.

In addition, the ASV processing system executes online versions of the AI-based solutions described in this document targeting the autonomous detection of areas of interest based on the radioactivity data received from the gliders, as well as on-line incremental radioactivity mapping from the real-time spatiotemporal fusion of the currently available radioactivity measurements. Both tasks are crucial for enabling ad-hoc glider mission adaptation and rescheduling, while allowing for increased situation awareness, improved mission planning and efficient communication to the base station via 4G.

Testing and Validation

Development and validation of the AI-based software modules on the on-board devices of the RAMONES vehicles is ongoing and subsystem testing has been performed in a lab setting. Regarding the underwater glider vehicles, testing in the final setup is planned for Q1 2024. This includes testing of acoustic channel communication in a relevant environment, sensor data acquisition and transfer as well as γ Sniffer measurement reading and processing. The current development status of the processing system of the ASV includes environment setup and implementation of the RAMONES communication stack as well as the integration and adaptation of the AI-based time-series processing modules described in Section 3 on the ASV processing platform (Jetson Nano). These operations together with the testing of the system in a relevant environment are planned for completion in Q1-Q2 2024.

6. Closing Remarks

This deliverable provides an overview of the 2nd release of AI-based solutions for processing and analysing data collected from the RAMONES instruments. To anticipate challenges of detector deployment using underwater gliders in large scan volumes, a high-level simulation environment has been developed, to study the characteristics of the radioactivity measurements (time-series) resulting from different combinations of glider trajectories and radioactivity sources. The simulation results indicate that detection of point sources lying on the sea bottom is virtually impossible in normal operating conditions of underwater gliders, due to radioactivity shielding from the water. On the other hand, the results are encouraging for the effective mapping of large areas/volumes. The simulations show that mapping accuracy depends on the radioactivity distribution, the localization accuracy, the type of scan trajectories and their spacing, as well as the method used to propagate the measurements to the entire scan volume. Regarding the latter, a novel MLP-based interpolation method has been developed that achieves higher accuracy in most cases with notable speedup with respect to typical linear interpolation implementations. An important outcome of the simulations is that they allow to better understand the trade-off between mapping accuracy and time required to execute the selected scan paths.

Regarding processing of time-series, besides the MLP-based interpolation method for highly sparse measurements, algorithms have been developed for preprocessing and analysing the data collected by the γ Sniffers and the SUGI instruments. In addition, deep learning frameworks have been developed to properly process the imaging data collected by SUGI and CHERI.

This document also presents the current state of the integration of the proposed solution to the selected computation platforms of the RAMONES vehicles. **As these platforms are currently being finalized, an update of this document will be provided within M42**, presenting the finalized versions of the AI software components, as well as their validation on the vehicles, tested on a relevant environment.

References

- [1] Mildenhall, B., Srinivasan, P. P., Tancik, M., Barron, J. T., Ramamoorthi, R., & Ng, R. (2021). Nerf: Representing scenes as neural radiance fields for view synthesis. *Communications of the ACM*, 65(1), 99-106.
- [2] Tancik, M., Srinivasan, P., Mildenhall, B., Fridovich-Keil, S., Raghavan, N., Singhal, U., Ramamoorthi, R., Barron, J. & Ng, R. (2020). Fourier features let networks learn high frequency functions in low dimensional domains. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33, 7537-7547.
- [3] Venkataramanan S., Psomas B., Avrithis Y., Kijak E., Amsaleg L., Karantzalos K., 2022. It Takes Two to Tango: Mixup for Deep Metric Learning, International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR).
- [4] Kakogeorgiou I., Gidaris S., Psomas B., Avrithis Y., Bursuc A., Karantzalos K., Komodakis N. 2022. What to Hide from Your Students: Attention-Guided Masked Image Modeling, European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV).
- [5] Lehner, Z. He & F. Zhang (2004), 4/spl pi/ compton imaging using a 3-d position-sensitive CdZnTe detector via weighted list-mode maximum likelihood, *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 51, 1618.
- [6] Puzenat, J. Escartín, J.-E. Martelat, T. Barreyre, S. Le Moine Bauer, P. Nomikou et al. (2021), Shallow-water hydrothermalism at Milos (Greece): Nature, distribution, heat fluxes and impact on ecosystems, *Marine Geology*, 438, 106521
- [7] Psomas, Kakogeorgiou, Karantzalos, Avrithis, 2023. Keep It SimPool: Who Said Supervised Transformers Suffer from Attention Deficit? IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision, ICCV 2023

Appendix

High-level simulator code structure

diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp...
Melkon Chatsikian authored 10 months ago

d0624bb8

Name	Last commit	Last update
..		
inputs	Changed deviation method for trajectories, calculation of metrics implement...	1 year ago
diffuse.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
env_creation_visual.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
glider_curve.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
interpolate.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
main.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
mlp.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
radiation_intensity_calculation.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
radiation_plots.py	Changed deviation method for trajectories, calculation of metrics implement...	1 year ago
requirements.txt	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
results.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
run_script.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago
utils.py	diffusion scenario added, spiral curve support added, scipy and mlp interpol...	10 months ago

γ Sniffer data processing code

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository named 'data-analysis' (Private). The repository is owned by 'mdouskos' and has 1 branch and 0 tags. It contains 2 commits. The repository description is 'Repository for hosting code for analysing the data collected by the RAMONES instruments'. The repository includes files: LICENSE, README.md, environment.yml, and plot_counts.py. The README file is selected and shows the repository name and description. The right sidebar shows repository statistics: 0 stars, 2 watching, 0 forks, and 0 releases published. The language statistics show Python at 100.0%.

File	Commit	Time
LICENSE	Initial commit	10 months ago
README.md	Initial commit	10 months ago
environment.yml	Add script for plotting counts from SPE files	10 months ago
plot_counts.py	Add script for plotting counts from SPE files	10 months ago

SUGI custom API

The screenshot shows the GitHub interface for the repository 'ramones-gamma-imaging'. The repository is private and has 4 branches and 0 tags. The current branch is 64 commits ahead of the main branch. The commit history shows a recent commit by 'mdouskos' adding simulated CPS for Milos SUGI data. The repository contains files such as 'docs', 'gds_100', 'utils', '.gitignore', 'CHANGELOG', 'README.md', 'TO-DOs.txt', 'requirements.txt', and 'setup.py'. The README section is visible, showing the repository name and a brief description: 'Gamma Imaging techniques for the RAMONES project'.